

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 21/02/2026

Accepted: 16/03/2026

Published: 23/03/2026

Citation: Punitha N, Kalavathi A (2026) Some Exact Solutions of Unsteady Incompressible Coupled Stress Fluids with Topology Conservation of Vorticity Vector Field by Ansatz Method. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(10): 704-712. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i10.265>

* **Corresponding author.**thirunithasiddhu@gmail.com**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Some Exact Solutions of Unsteady Incompressible Coupled Stress Fluids with Topology Conservation of Vorticity Vector Field by Ansatz Method

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary objective of this study is to obtain exact analytical solutions for unsteady incompressible couple stress fluid flows using the Ansatz method. The study is motivated by the need to better understand the influence of microstructural effects present in couple stress fluids, which arise in various engineering and biological applications. In addition, the work aims to establish and verify the topology conservation equation associated with the vorticity vector field in order to investigate the structural and rotational characteristics of the flow. **Method:** The governing equations for unsteady incompressible couple stress fluids are formulated based on the fundamental principles of fluid mechanics. From the vorticity transport equation, a topology conservation equation related to the vorticity vector field is derived. The resulting higher-order nonlinear partial differential equations are then analyzed using the Ansatz method by assuming an appropriate vector potential. This approach simplifies the complex system of equations and allows the derivation of exact analytical solutions for specific flow configurations. Furthermore, graphical representations are employed to examine the influence of viscosity and couple stress parameters on the velocity and vorticity fields. **Findings:** The study successfully derives exact analytical solutions for selected unsteady flow configurations of couple stress fluids. The obtained expressions for the velocity and vorticity fields are shown to satisfy the derived topology conservation equation, confirming the mathematical validity and consistency of the model. The graphical analysis illustrates that variations in viscosity and couple stress parameters significantly influence the structure and magnitude of the velocity field as well as the behavior of the vorticity distribution within the fluid. **Novelty:** The novelty of this work lies in the application of the Ansatz method to solve higher-order nonlinear equations governing unsteady incompressible couple stress fluid flows while incorporating the topology conservation of the vorticity vector field. Unlike many existing studies that rely primarily on numerical or approximate techniques, this research provides explicit analytical solutions together with graphical analysis. The results contribute to a deeper theoretical understanding of the structural properties and dynamic behavior of couple stress fluids under unsteady flow conditions.

Keywords: Unsteady incompressible couple stress fluid; topology conservation equation; couple stress parameters

1 Introduction

The study of exact solutions for three-dimensional incompressible fluid flows has evolved significantly through the integration of geometry, topology, and analytical methods. A rigorous mathematical description of fluid motion from a geometric viewpoint was developed by Vladimir Arnold and Boris Khesin⁽¹⁾, who demonstrated how hydrodynamic equations can be interpreted using modern topological and differential geometric tools. Their work clarified the structural invariants that characterize ideal fluid motion and laid the foundation for subsequent topological investigations in fluid mechanics.

Further analytical progress was made by Chang et al.⁽²⁾, who formulated general steady-state solutions within theoretical flow models, providing a broader understanding of equilibrium configurations. Dai et al.⁽³⁾ contributed to solution methodologies by introducing a hybrid Exp-function ansatz technique for nonlinear differential equations, enabling the construction of explicit analytical expressions in complex flow problems.

Exact three-dimensional solutions applicable to both Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids were obtained by Daniel D. Joseph⁽⁴⁾, extending analytical treatments beyond classical viscous models. In another study, Joseph⁽⁵⁾ proposed carefully chosen ansatz forms of vector potentials to derive new exact solutions for couple stress fluids. He also examined how the topological structure of vorticity is maintained in viscous and inviscid flows Joseph⁽⁶⁾, emphasizing the persistence of vortex configurations under certain flow conditions.

The representation of incompressible velocity fields through vector potentials has its origins in the classical analysis of Horace Lamb⁽⁷⁾, who established the relationship between velocity and vorticity in fluid motion. From a topological perspective, Keith Moffatt⁽⁸⁾ analyzed the linking and knotting properties of vortex lines, and later expanded these ideas by identifying additional structural features and unresolved questions in fluid dynamics⁽⁹⁾.

In magneto hydrodynamic contexts, Khan et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ derived exact solutions describing the flow of a couple stress fluid influenced by magnetic and thermal effects, thereby combining fluid mechanics with electromagnetic interactions. Boyland⁽¹¹⁾ explored the role of topological dynamics in two-dimensional mixing by applying Thurston–Nielsen theory to characterize fluid stretching and folding. Complementing these studies, Clifford Truesdell⁽¹²⁾ provided a detailed examination of vorticity kinematics, enhancing the theoretical framework for understanding vortex evolution.

Inspired by these theoretical and analytical advancements, the present work investigates unsteady incompressible couple stress fluid flow without body forces. By selecting suitable ansatz representations for the vector potential, exact solutions are constructed. These solutions yield explicit expressions for both velocity and vorticity fields while adhering to established principles governing topological preservation in fluid motion.

2 Methodology

2.1 Equations of motion

As the motion proceeds, Trudsell¹³ offers a necessary and sufficient condition that says that when the flux of an arbitrary vector field S passes through an arbitrary material surface $Topology$, the vorticity field in inviscid and viscous fluid flows is conserved.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\omega \cdot \nabla)S - (S \cdot \nabla)\omega + S(\nabla \cdot \omega) = 0 \tag{2.1.1}$$

Furthermore, for vector tube S to exist, the following conditions must be satisfied:

$$S \times \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\omega \cdot \nabla)S - (S \cdot \nabla)\omega \right) = 0 \tag{2.1.2}$$

Here, ω is the generating vector field.

An arbitrary vector field's topological conservation condition is satisfied by

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\omega \cdot \nabla)S - (S \cdot \nabla)\omega = \lambda S \tag{2.1.3}$$

In a smooth domain of the Euclidean space $\Omega \subseteq R^3$, Stokes⁴ first proposed theories and equations for couple stress fluid flows. The basic governing equations for unsteady flow of incompressible couple stress fluid with conservative body forces are as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot u = 0 \tag{2.1.4}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + (u \cdot \nabla)u = -\nabla p + \nabla \varphi + \nu \nabla^2 u - \mu \nabla^4 u \tag{2.1.5}$$

Where $u(x, t)$ is a time dependent vector field (or) velocity field, $\nabla \varphi$ is the conservative body force, ν is the coefficient of kinematic viscosity ($\nu > 0$), μ is the couple stress velocity parameter ($\mu > 0$) and $p(x, t)$ is the pressure function. where

$$\nabla = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \text{ - Hamilton operator}$$

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \text{ - Laplace operator and}$$

$$\nabla^4 = \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial z^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial z^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^2 \partial z^2} \text{ - Biharmonic operator}$$

Using the curl of equations (2.1.5), the vorticity equation for the incompressible couple stress fluid flow is given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + \nabla \times (\omega \times u) - \nu \nabla^2 \omega + \mu \nabla^4 \omega = 0 \tag{2.1.6}$$

where $\omega = \nabla \times u$ (or) *curl* u

In the context of incompressible couple stress fluid flows, we must determine if topology conservation of vorticity field lines occurs or not. If there is such flow, the vorticity vector field must satisfy both equations (2.1.3) and (2.1.5) simultaneously. In the next section, exact solutions for couple stress fluid flows with topology-conserving vorticity fields are derived which satisfies equations (2.1.5) and (2.1.6) respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Solution methodology

It is well known that solving nonlinear partial differential equations precisely is difficult. Various methods have been devised to pinpoint precise solutions for these kinds of equations. Since ordinary differential equations are very easy to handle, one of the best approaches is to utilize the required transformations to convert the provided nonlinear partial differential equations into ordinary differential equations. Many nonlinear partial differential equations were reduced to ordinary differential equations using traveling wave transformations. The resulting ordinary differential equations are nonlinear, making it difficult to find the requisite solutions.

Consider nonlinear partial differential equations (2.1.5) for couple stress fluid flows of higher order than the Navier-Stokes equations. Finding accurate solutions to the Navier-Stoke equation is especially hard. As a result, finding precise solutions to couple stress fluid flows is significantly more challenging and solutions for such flows are extremely rare in the literature and are primarily limited to one-dimensional or two-dimensional flows. Because the flow is incompressible and equation (2.1.4) is satisfied, one can generate the necessary velocity field from the vector potential A , which satisfies this equation. The general form of the vector potential is in the form

$$A = e^{at} (A_1, A_2, A_3) \tag{3.1.1}$$

Where $A_i(x, y, z)$ is a scalar function, $A_i(x, y, z) = f_i(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z)$

Hence the vector potential takes the form

$$A = e^{at} (f_1(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z), f_2(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z), f_3(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z)) \tag{3.1.2}$$

Where f_1, f_2, f_3 are functions to be determined.

By taking curl of equation (3.1.2), we get the velocity field as

$$v = \nabla \times A = e^{at} \begin{pmatrix} a_2 f_3'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) - a_3 f_2'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) \\ a_3 f_1'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) - a_1 f_3'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) \\ a_1 f_2'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) - a_2 f_1'(a_1x + a_2y + a_3z) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1.3}$$

Clearly, the velocity field satisfies equation (2.1.4).

Now, the vorticity field is obtained as

$$\omega = \nabla \times v = e^{at} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 a_2 f_2''(u) + a_1 a_3 f_3''(u) - (a_2^2 + a_3^2) f_1''(u) \\ a_1 a_2 f_1''(u) + a_2 a_3 f_3''(u) - (a_1^2 + a_3^2) f_2''(u) \\ a_1 a_3 f_1''(u) + a_2 a_3 f_2''(u) - (a_1^2 + a_2^2) f_3''(u) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1.4}$$

This is the solution of Navier – Stokes equation, if the above equation satisfies equation
 Substituting equation (3.1.4) in equation (2.1.6), we get

$$e^{at} \begin{pmatrix} a_1(a_2F_2(u) + a_3F_3(u) - (a_2^2 + a_3^2)F_1(u)) \\ a_2(a_1F_1(u) + a_3F_3(u) - (a_1^2 + a_3^2)F_2(u)) \\ a_3(a_1F_1(u) + a_2F_2(u) - (a_1^2 + a_2^2)F_3(u)) \end{pmatrix} = 0 \tag{3.1.5}$$

Where

$$F_1(u) = af_1''(u) + \delta(\delta\mu f_1^{(6)}(u) - \vartheta f_1^{(4)}(u))$$

$$F_2(u) = af_2''(u) + \delta(\delta\mu f_2^{(6)}(uz) - \vartheta f_2^{(4)}(u))$$

$$F_3(u) = af_3''(u) + \delta(\delta\mu f_3^{(6)}(u) - \vartheta f_3^{(4)}(u))$$

$$\text{where } \delta = a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 \text{ and } u = a_1x + a_2y + a_3z \tag{3.1.6}$$

Hence the vector potential given by equation (3.1.2) will be the solution if equation (3.1.5) is satisfied. The corresponding sufficient condition is

$$F_1(u) = F_2(u) = F_3(u) = 0 \tag{3.1.7}$$

Hence, the solution of equation (3.1.6) becomes

$$f_1(u) = c_1e^{\alpha u} + c_2e^{-\alpha u} + c_3e^{\beta u} + c_4e^{-\beta u} + c_5u + c_6 \tag{3.1.8}$$

Where $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6$ are arbitrary constants and

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{\vartheta + \sqrt{\vartheta^2 - 4a\mu}}{2\delta\mu}} \text{ and } \beta = \sqrt{\frac{\vartheta - \sqrt{\vartheta^2 - 4a\mu}}{2\delta\mu}} \tag{3.1.9}$$

In order to derive explicit periodic solutions for the couple stress fluid flows, we must solve equation (3.1.9) for the parameter ‘ a ’ (α imaginary) Solving we get

$$a = -\delta(\delta\mu + \nu) \tag{3.1.10}$$

Substitute equation (3.1.10) in equation (3.1.8) and solving, we get

$$f_1(u) = A_1 \cos u + A_2 \sin u \tag{3.1.11}$$

Similarly, we can solve the exact solutions of the remaining equations in equation (3.1.6) as

$$f_2(u) = B_1 \cos u + B_2 \sin u \tag{3.1.12}$$

$$f_3(u) = C_1 \cos u + C_2 \sin u \tag{3.1.13}$$

Where $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are arbitrary parameters.

Substituting the values of f_1, f_2, f_3 in equation (2.2), we obtain the velocity potential as

$$A = e^{at} (A_1 \cos u + A_2 \sin u, B_1 \cos u + B_2 \sin u, C_1 \cos u + C_2 \sin u) \tag{3.1.14}$$

Accordingly, the precise solution to the Navier-Stokes equation which satisfies equations (1.4) and (1.5) is provided by

$$v = e^{at} (M_1 \cos u + M_2 \sin u, M_3 \cos u + M_4 \sin u, M_5 \cos u + M_6 \sin u) \tag{3.1.15}$$

Where

$$M_1 = a_2 C_2 - a_3 B_2, M_2 = a_3 B_1 - a_2 C_1, M_3 = a_3 A_2 - a_1 C_2, \\ M_4 = a_1 C_1 - a_3 A_1, M_5 = a_1 B_2 - a_2 A_2, M_6 = a_2 A_1 - a_1 B_1$$

And corresponding vorticity field is obtained as

$$\omega = e^{at} (N_1 \cos u + N_2 \sin u, N_3 \cos u + N_4 \sin u, N_5 \cos u + N_6 \sin u) \tag{3.1.16}$$

Where

$$N_1 = (a_2^2 + a_3^2) A_1 - a_1 (a_2 B_1 + a_3 C_1), N_2 = (a_2^2 + a_3^2) A_2 - a_1 (a_2 B_2 + a_3 C_2), \\ N_3 = (a_1^2 + a_3^2) B_1 - a_2 (a_1 A_1 + a_3 C_1), N_4 = (a_1^2 + a_3^2) B_2 - a_2 (a_1 A_2 + a_3 C_2), \\ N_5 = (a_1^2 + a_2^2) C_1 - a_3 (a_1 A_1 + a_2 B_1), N_6 = (a_1^2 + a_2^2) C_2 - a_3 (a_1 A_2 + a_2 B_2)$$

Graphical visualization of the vector field is given through figures 1- 4 for different couple stress fluids like Mercury, milk, glycerin and heavy oil.

Fig 1. Plot of velocity vector field for Mercury ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -2.0; a_3 = 3.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 2.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 1.0; B_2 = 0.0; C_2 = 2.0; \nu = 1.526; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Fig 2. Plot of velocity vector field for Whole milk ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -1.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 2.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 2.12; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

From the above figures, we can conclude that the vector field shows drastic variations with respect to kinematic viscosity.

For vorticity conservation, this flow must meet equation (3.1.3). Substituting the velocity and vorticity fields into this equation, the equation will be satisfied if $\lambda = -\delta(\delta\mu + \nu)$. Thus, we arrived the exact periodic solution for incompressible couple stress fluid flow, and the vorticity field is topology conserved if $\lambda = -\delta(\delta\mu + \nu)$.

Particular solution 1:

By setting all of the parameters A_2, B_2, C_1 to zero, we can examine the specific periodic solutions found in (3.1.15).

Accordingly, the exact periodic solution of Navier Stokes equation satisfying equations (2.1.4) and (2.1.5) is given by

$$v = e^{at} \begin{pmatrix} a_2 C_2 \cos u + a_3 B_1 \sin u \\ -a_1 C_2 \cos u - a_3 A_1 \sin u \\ -a_2 A_2 \cos u + (a_2 A_1 - a_1 B_1) \sin u \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1.17}$$

Fig 3. Plot of velocity vector field for Glycerin ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = 2.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 2.0; B_1 = 2.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 1.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.49; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Fig 4. Plot of velocity vector field for heavy oil ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -1.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 2.0; A_2 = 2.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 0.66; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Corresponding vorticity vector is

$$\omega = e^{\alpha t} (P_1 \cos u + P_2 \sin u, P_3 \cos u + P_4 \sin u, P_5 \cos u + P_6 \sin u) \tag{3.1.18}$$

Where

$$P_1 = (a_2^2 + a_3^2) A_1 - a_1 (a_2 B_1), P_2 = -a_1 (a_2 B_2 + a_3 C_2),$$

$$P_3 = (a_1^2 + a_3^2) B_1 - a_2 (a_1 A_1), P_4 = -a_2 (a_3 C_2),$$

$$P_5 = -a_3 (a_1 A_1 + a_2 B_1), P_6 = (a_1^2 + a_2^2) C_2$$

Graphical visualization of velocity vector field for various couple stress fluids are presented through figures 5- 8. From figures, we can conclude that with varying kinematic viscosity, the vector field is varying drastically.

Fig 5. Plot of velocity vector field for Mercury ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -2.0; a_3 = 3.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 0.0; A_2 = 0.0; B_2 = 0.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.526; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

For vorticity conservation, the flow must satisfy equation (2.1.3). Substitute the velocity field and the corresponding vorticity field in equation (2.1.3), the equation will be satisfied when $\lambda = -\delta(\delta\mu + \nu)$. Hence, we obtain the exact periodic solution for incompressible couple stress fluid flows for which the vorticity field is topology conserved when $\lambda = -\delta(\delta\mu + \nu)$.

Fig 6. Plot of velocity vector field for Whole milk($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -1.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 0.0; A_2 = 0.0; B_2 = 0.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 2.12; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Fig 7. Plot of velocity vector field for Glycerin($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = 2.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 0.0; A_2 = 0.0; B_2 = 0.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.49; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$).

Fig 8. Plot of velocity vector field for heavy oil($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -1.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 0.0; A_2 = 0.0; B_2 = 0.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.49; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Particular solution II:

When all the parameters are allowed to equal one, an explicit example is produced ($A_1 = A_2 = B_1 = B_2 = C_1 = C_2 = 1$) and $a_1 = 1, a_2 = -2, a_3 = 2$, we get exact periodic solution of couple stress fluid flow in the form

$$v = e^{-9(9\mu+\nu)} \begin{pmatrix} -4\cos(x-2y-3z) + 4\sin(x-2y-3z) \\ \cos(x-2y-3z) - 1\sin(x-2y-3z) \\ 3\cos(x-2y-3z) - 3\sin(x-2y-3z) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1.19}$$

And corresponding vorticity field is

$$\omega = e^{-9(9\mu+\nu)} \begin{pmatrix} 8(\cos(x-2y-3z) - \sin(x-2y-3z)) \\ 11(\cos(x-2y-3z) - \sin(x-2y-3z)) \\ 7(\cos(x-2y-3z) - \sin(x-2y-3z)) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3.1.20}$$

Diagrammatic representation of velocity vector for different couple stress fluids are shown through figures 9- 12 for a particular case. It is clear that, the velocity vector field varies for varying kinematic viscosity.

Fig 9. Plot of velocity vector field for Mercury ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -2.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 1.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.526; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Fig 10. Plot of velocity vector field for Whole milk ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -2.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 1.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 2.12; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

Fig 11. Plot of velocity vector field for Glycerin ($a_1 = 1.0; a_2 = -2.0; a_3 = 2.0; A_1 = 1.0; B_1 = 1.0; C_1 = 1.0; A_2 = 1.0; B_2 = 1.0; C_2 = 1.0; \nu = 1.49; \mu = 0.2; t = 1.0$)

For topology conservation, the flow must satisfy equation (2.1.3). The topology conservation equation (2.1.3) is satisfied when $\lambda = -9(9\mu + \nu)$. Hence, we obtained the exact periodic solution for the particular case II when $\lambda = -9(9\mu + \nu)$.

4 Conclusion

This study has examined the topology conservation of the vorticity field in unsteady incompressible couple stress fluid flows and has derived exact periodic solutions using the Ansatz method. The analytical framework developed in this work enables the formulation of explicit expressions for both the velocity and vorticity vector fields while preserving the topological structure of the flow. The obtained solutions satisfy the governing equations of couple stress fluid dynamics and the associated topology conservation condition, thereby confirming the mathematical consistency and validity of the proposed model.

Fig 12. Plot of velocity vector field for heavy oil ($a_1 = 1.0$; $a_2 = -2.0$; $a_3 = 2.0$; $A_1 = 1.0$; $B_1 = 1.0$; $C_1 = 1.0$; $A_2 = 1.0$; $B_2 = 1.0$; $C_2 = 1.0$; $\nu = 0.66$; $\mu = 0.1$; $t = 1.0$)

The analytical results provide important insights into the structural behavior of the vorticity field and the rotational dynamics of couple stress fluids. To further explore the physical implications of the solutions, graphical analyses of the velocity field were performed for different values of kinematic viscosity corresponding to Mercury, Whole Milk, Glycerin, and Oil. The results clearly demonstrate that variations in viscosity significantly influence the magnitude and distribution of the velocity vector field. Moreover, the couple stress parameter plays a crucial role in modifying the flow structure due to the microstructural effects inherent in couple stress fluids.

Overall, the present work contributes to the analytical understanding of unsteady non-Newtonian fluid flows by integrating topology conservation with exact solution techniques. The proposed approach provides a useful framework for analyzing more complex fluid systems and may serve as a foundation for future studies involving additional physical effects such as magnetic fields, thermal transport, or porous media interactions.

5 Acknowledgements

About authors; N.Punitha and Dr.A.Kalavathi serve as Assistant Professors

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